

New explicit formula for computing Bernoulli Numbers

Valerio Venturi

ABSTRACT. Bernoulli Numbers are a sequences of rational numbers which appear frequently in mathematical analysis. It is described a new explicit formula for computing Bernoulli numbers by using Weierstrass factorization theorem on hyperbolic cosine, Maclaurin series of hyperbolic cosine, binomial expansion and values of Riemann zeta function for even positive integers as argument.

It is possible express an integer power of hyperbolic cosine as a linear combination of hyperbolic cosine by using binomial expansion¹ on hyperbolic cosine in terms of exponential function²

$$(1) \quad (\cosh(x))^n = \frac{(e^x + e^{-x})^n}{2^n} = \frac{n!}{2^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{e^{kx}}{k!} \frac{e^{-(n-k)x}}{(n-k)!} = \frac{n!}{2^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{e^{(2k-n)x}}{(n-k)!k!}$$

If the exponent is even

$$(2) \quad (\cosh(x))^{2n} = \frac{(2n)!}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^{2n} \frac{e^{(2k-2n)x}}{(2n-k)!k!} = \frac{(2n)!}{4^n} \sum_{k=-n}^n \frac{e^{2kx}}{(n-k)!(n+k)!}$$

$$(3) \quad (\cosh(x))^{2n} = \frac{(2n)!}{4^n} \left(\frac{1}{n!^2} + 2 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{\cosh(2kx)}{(n-k)!(n+k)!} \right)$$

If the exponent is odd

$$(4) \quad (\cosh(x))^{2n+1} = \frac{(2n+1)!}{4^n 2} \sum_{k=0}^{2n+1} \frac{e^{(2k-2n-1)x}}{(2n+1-k)!k!} = \frac{(2n+1)!}{4^n 2} \sum_{k=-n}^{n+1} \frac{e^{(2k-1)x}}{(n+1-k)!(n+k)!}$$

$$(5) \quad (\cosh(x))^{2n+1} = \frac{(2n+1)!}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{\cosh((2k+1)x)}{(n-k)!(n+k+1)!}$$

It is also possible express an integer power of hyperbolic cosine as an integer power of Weierstrass product of hyperbolic cosine, then it is possible express hyperbolic cosine as an even-power series by multipling by each others all binomials of Weierstrass product of hyperbolic cosine. Each coefficient of $2b$ -degree term is an infinite sum of products of b element, each element of the b -elements products is a square of odd integer number (zeros of hyperbolic cosine). Each b -elements products is a subset of the set of zeros of hyperbolic cosine. Each element of b -elements products have a multiplicity less than or equal to n , because n is the power of hyperbolic cosine and also the power of each binomial of Weierstrass product of hyperbolic cosine³

$$(6) \quad \left(\cosh\left(\frac{\pi}{2}x\right) \right)^n = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 + \frac{x^2}{(2k-1)^2} \right)^n = \sum_{b=0}^{\infty} x^{2b} \sum_{a_1=1}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{a_b=1}^{\infty} \prod_{j=1}^b \frac{1}{(2a_j-1)^2}$$

$a_j \in A \subset \mathbb{N}, m(k_j) \leq n, |A| = b$

The Maclaurin series of hyperbolic cosine is²

$$(7) \quad \cosh(x) = \sum_{b=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^{2b}}{(2b)!}$$

If we combine equation (3) and equation (7) for even power of hyperbolic cosine we get

$$(8) \quad \left(\cosh\left(\frac{\pi}{2}x\right)\right)^{2n} = \frac{(2n)!}{4^n} \left(\frac{1}{n!} + 2 \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{(n-k)!(n+k)!} \sum_{b=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\pi kx)^{2b}}{(2b)!}\right)$$

$$(9) \quad \left(\cosh\left(\frac{\pi}{2}x\right)\right)^{2n} = \frac{(2n)!}{4^n} \left(\frac{1}{n!} + 2 \sum_{b=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\pi x)^{2b}}{(2b)!} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{k^{2b}}{(n-k)!(n+k)!}\right)$$

If we combine equation (6) and equation (9) for even power of hyperbolic cosine we get

$$(10) \quad \sum_{a_1=1}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{a_b=1}^{\infty} \prod_{j=1}^b \frac{1}{(2a_j-1)^2} = \frac{(2n)!}{(2b)!} \frac{\pi^{2b}}{2^{2n-1}} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{k^{2b}}{(n-k)!(n+k)!}$$

If we combine equation (5) and equation (7) for odd power of hyperbolic cosine we get

$$(11) \quad \left(\cosh\left(\frac{\pi}{2}x\right)\right)^{2n+1} = \frac{(2n+1)!}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{1}{(n-k)!(n+k+1)!} \sum_{b=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\pi(k+2^{-1})x)^{2b}}{(2b)!}$$

$$(12) \quad \left(\cosh\left(\frac{\pi}{2}x\right)\right)^{2n+1} = \frac{(2n+1)!}{4^n} \sum_{b=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\pi x)^{2b}}{(2b)!} \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(2k+1)^{2b}}{(n-k)!(n+k+1)!}$$

If we combine equation (6) and equation (12) for odd power of hyperbolic cosine we get

$$(13) \quad \sum_{a_1=1}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{a_b=1}^{\infty} \prod_{j=1}^b \frac{1}{(2a_j-1)^2} = \frac{(2n+1)!}{(2b)!} \frac{\pi^{2b}}{4^n} \sum_{k=0}^n \frac{(2k+1)^{2b}}{(n-k)!(n+k+1)!} 4^b$$

It is possible express Riemann zeta function for even positive integers as argument in terms of Bernoulli numbers⁴

$$(14) \quad \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{2b}} = \frac{|B_{2b}|}{2} \frac{(2\pi)^{2b}}{(2b)!} = \frac{|B_{2b}|}{2} \frac{\pi^{2b}}{(2b)!} 4^b$$

Then it is possible express the sum of negative even powers of all odd numbers in terms of Bernoulli numbers

$$(15) \quad \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^{2b}} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^{2b}}\right) \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{2b}} = \left(1 - \frac{1}{4^b}\right) \frac{|B_{2b}|}{2} \frac{\pi^{2b}}{(2b)!} 4^b = (4^b - 1) \frac{|B_{2b}|}{2} \frac{\pi^{2b}}{(2b)!}$$

If b is equal to 1 we have the special case:

$$(16) \quad \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2} = (4-1) \frac{|B_2|}{2} \frac{\pi^2}{2!} = \frac{\pi^2}{8}$$

It is possible express the sum of -2b powers of all odd numbers in terms of b-power of the equation (16) and equation (6) if each element of b-elements products have a multiplicity less than or equal to b-1, a special case of equation (6)

$$(17) \quad \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^{2b}} = \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)^2}\right)^b - \sum_{a_1=1}^{\infty} \dots \sum_{a_b=1}^{\infty} \prod_{j=1}^b \frac{1}{(2a_j-1)^2}$$

$a_j \in A \subset \mathbb{N}, m(k_j) \leq b-1, |A|=b$

If we combine equation (17), equation (14) and equation (13) if b is an even multiple of 2 we get

$$(18) \quad (4^{2b} - 1) \frac{|B_{4b}|}{2} \frac{\pi^{4b}}{(4b)!} = \frac{\pi^{4b}}{64^b} - \frac{(4b-1)!}{(4b)!} \frac{\pi^{4b}}{4^{2b-1} 16^b} \sum_{k=0}^{2b-1} \frac{(2k+1)^{4b}}{(2b-k-1)!(2b+k)!}$$

$$(19) \quad |B_{4b}| = 2 \frac{(4b)!}{16^b - 1} \left(\frac{1}{64^b} - \frac{1}{b 256^b} \sum_{k=0}^{2b-1} \frac{(2k+1)^{4b}}{(2b-k-1)!(2b+k)!}\right)$$

If we combine equation (17), equation (14) and equation (10) if b is an odd multiple of 2 we get

$$(4^{2b+1} - 1) \frac{|B_{4b+2}|}{2} \frac{\pi^{4b+2}}{(4b+2)!} = \frac{\pi^{4b+2}}{8^{2b+1}} - \frac{(4b)!}{(4b+2)!} \frac{\pi^{4b+2}}{2^{4b-1}} \sum_{k=1}^{2b} \frac{k^{4b+2}}{(2b-k)!(2b+k)!}$$

$$|B_{4b+2}| = 2 \frac{(4b+2)!}{4^{2b+1} - 1} \left(\frac{1}{8^{2b+1}} - \frac{1}{(2b+1)(4b+1)16^b} \sum_{k=1}^{2b} \frac{k^{4b+2}}{(2b-k)!(2b+k)!}\right)$$

REFERENCES

1. G.A. Korn, T.M. Korn, "Mathematical handbook for scientists and engineers" , McGraw-Hill (1968) [Zbl 0177.29301](#)
2. [Abramowitz, Milton](#); Stegun, Irene A. (1970). *Handbook of Mathematical Functions with Formulas, Graphs, and Mathematical Tables*. New York: Dover Publications. Ninth printing.
3. Olver, Frank W. J.; Lozier, Daniel M.; Boisvert, Ronald F.; Clark, Charles W., eds. (2010), "[Hyperbolic functions](#)", *NIST Handbook of Mathematical Functions*, Cambridge University Press, ISBN 978-0-521-19225-5, MR 2723248.
4. Abramowitz, M.; Stegun, I. A. (1972), "§23.1: Bernoulli and Euler Polynomials and the Euler-Maclaurin Formula", *Handbook of Mathematical Functions with Formulas, Graphs, and Mathematical Tables* (9th printing ed.), New York: Dover Publications, pp. 804–806.